

STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF OPTIONS FOR ASIAN AND EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

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Annotation: The main goal and task of this article is to determine alternative option prices and evaluate the option price based on the binomial model.

Key words: Option, alternative prices, option price, binomial model.

СТАТИСТИЧЕСКАЯ ОЦЕНКА ОПЦИОНОВ ДЛЯ СТРАН АЗИИ И ЕВРОПЫ

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Аннотация: Основная цель и задача данной статьи — определить альтернативные цены опционов и оценить стоимость опциона на основе биномиальной модели.

Ключевые слова: Опцион, альтернативные цены, цена опциона, биномиальная модель.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi va vazifasi opsiyon muqobil narxlarini aniqlash va binomial model asosida opsiyon narxining qiymatini baholashdir.

Key words: opsiyon, muqobil narxlar, opsiyon narxi, binomial model.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid acceleration of economic growth in developed countries requires the modernization of their economies. This, in turn, necessitates the implementation of appropriate investment activity assessment models that ensure the realization of relevant innovative projects. This process is typically characterized by the availability of many alternatives for investing limited resources, which leads to the problem of determining the optimal direction for their use. As a financial instrument, selection today involves determining the alternative value of the future purchase or sale price of a product. The problem of determining alternative prices for options is of great importance today, as it helps prevent the emergence of arbitrage situations. Traditional methods applied to other financial instruments do not allow for the correct determination of option values, since the risk indicator for assets underlying options changes depending on the value and duration of the underlying assets. To solve this problem, several models have been developed. The Black-Scholes model is one of the first developed and remains a fundamental model.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE RESEARCH TOPIC.

The binomial model for option pricing can be found in the following literature and articles: Hull J.C. *Options, Futures, and Other Derivatives*, pp. 321-383; James D. MacBeth, Larry J. Merville, *The Journal of Finance*, 34(5), 1173-1186, 1979;

Cheng-Few Lee, Gwo-Hshiong Tzeng, Shin-Yun Wang, *Expert Systems with Applications*, 29(2), 330-342, 2005.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article addresses current issues in economics. Probability theory, mathematical statistics, and financial mathematics methods have been utilized in the research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The issue of financial resource scarcity or expansion can be addressed not only through loans, credit, borrowing, or lending, but also by issuing and buying or selling securities. Securities are legal documents that confirm the holder's share in the property and income derived from that property, issued by corporations and organizations (regardless of ownership form), and give the right to transfer related rights to other parties. Securities are financial instruments, such as money or commodity documents, that grant the holder the right to own property and the right to receive a specific sum of money in the form of income. These include shares, bonds, letters of credit, promissory notes, checks, and others.

Securities are financial documents officially formatted in a specific way, which may include rights for certain persons. Securities can be registered in the name of a specific person (registered), in the name of the original buyer and transferred with their consent (order securities), or in some cases, not specifying the holder's name (bearer securities). The main types of securities are corporate shares, bonds, and government bonds. Securities provide the right to participate in corporate capital or to provide loans in exchange for receiving income in the form of dividends or interest. Since securities bring income to their holders, they are traded on stock exchanges at specific market prices. It is well-known that financing investments through securities is widespread in global practice. The foundation of financial investments consists of securities and their derivatives. Securities, through their investment appeal, also serve as instruments that determine the market activity of firms and companies.

The securities market can be divided into primary and derivative instruments. Primary instruments include shares, bonds, deposit and savings certificates, promissory notes, and other instruments. These instruments participate as primary tools in financing investment activities and play an important role in determining a company's investment activity.

Derivative financial instruments are securities whose returns (or losses) depend on the performance of one or more market indicators (indices). In financial

literature, derivative financial instruments are also referred to as created or secondary financial instruments. These include options, futures, deposit certificates, warrants, privatization certificates, coupons, and other financial instruments. Derivative securities serve to ensure the quality, profitability, market activity, and security of underlying assets.

An option (derived from the German word *Option*) is a contract between two parties that grants the right to buy or sell a specific asset at a predetermined price within a certain time frame. The concept of an option first emerged in the trade of agricultural products. The person who buys the option is called the buyer, and the person who sells the option is called the option seller. In 1973, the first standardized options for securities were introduced on the Chicago Stock Exchange. Prior to that, individual option contracts had non-standard characteristics and were customized to meet the specific needs of certain clients. By the late 1980s, options began to appear on exchanges in Amsterdam, London, Singapore, and Sydney, followed by exchanges in France, Japan, Belgium, Sweden, and New Zealand. Transactions involving options are typically carried out for the purpose of hedging a portfolio of securities (a portfolio is a collection of securities) or to gain profit from price differences, i.e., for speculative purposes.

To construct a mathematical model for the securities market, we need to address the following problems. The first problem is determining the duration of the obligations in the agreement. The second problem is establishing the price of the selling obligation in the option contract for this duration. The third problem is calculating the gain or profit for the parties involved in the contract. The fourth problem is determining the alternative price for both parties in order for there to be demand for the option in the market (i.e., a lower price for demand and a higher price for supply). Our main goal is to find answers to these questions. To build mathematical models for these problems, the following notations will be used:

1. For the agreed duration of the contract, the symbols N or n, t, T are used. Here, the problem is to determine N . In the case of a European option, $n = N$. In the case of an American option, the execution time of the contract obligation can occur at any moment within the interval $0 \leq n \leq N$, but the problem also involves determining the moment " n " at which the "obligation is fulfilled" (the moment the contract is terminated).

2. The problem of determining the agreed-upon buy or sell price " K " involves setting or forecasting the price based on the historical price changes (trends) of the stocks. If we denote the initial price of the stock at $n = 0$ as S_0 , then the price at time

$n = k$, where $0 \leq k \leq N$, is denoted as S_k . In many cases, the agreed price "K" is taken as the initial price of the stock (or asset) when the option contract is concluded, i.e., $K = S_0$. However, the agreed price "K" can also be chosen differently. The type of option depends on how "K" is selected. For example, in a put option, the agreed price is set accordingly

$$K = K_N = \min(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N),$$

call option

$$K = K_N = \max(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N),$$

in Asian options

$$K = K_N = \frac{1}{N+1} \sum_{k=0}^N S_k$$

it can be selected as.

At the initial moment ($n = 0$), that is, at the time the option contract is concluded, the price of the asset (stock) at that moment, S_0 is known. If it is agreed that $K = S_0$, the contract (option) is called a "zero-profit" option. If $K < S_0$, the option is considered profitable (in-the-money), and if $K > S_0$, the option is considered a losing (out-of-the-money) option. In the case of a European-style option, the seller prefers K to be higher, while the buyer wants K to be lower to achieve a profit (put option) or maximize their gains (call option). Afterward, the agreement is made based on this.

3. Objective function. The profit (or gain) of the parties from the option contract within the agreed (N or T) period, or during this period, depends on the price changes over time, which is why the income function is related to these changes

$$f_N = f_N(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N)$$

the symbol is used, where S_k is the price of the stock at time $n = k$ ($0 \leq k \leq N$). At $n = 0$, S_0 is the initial price of the stock at the moment the option contract is concluded. Since the future price of the stock is variable and random, S_k values are random quantities. In financial literature, the income function f_N is also called the objective, obligation, payment, or profit function. Depending on the contract terms and the agreement, options may take different forms. This function plays an important role in calculating the alternative prices of the contract.

To understand the essence of the objective function, let us consider a European-style call option, where the client agrees to buy the stock at a price K at the end of the N period. In this case, the buyer's profit is $f_N = (S_N - K)^+$ and to gain this profit, the buyer pays an average premium $C_N = Ef_N = E(S_N - K)^+$. The option holder, at time N , buys the stock not at the market price S_N , but at the agreed "K" price, thus gaining a profit of $(S_N - K)^+$. For example, based on this function, the issuer might offer to structure the option contract under such terms that the client will gain a profit f_N . To do this, the buyer will pay an average premium $C_N = Ef_N$. In the case of a European-style put option, the objective function takes the form $f_N = (K - S_N)^+$.

4. The next problem is to determine how much the client should pay as a premium for an option contract that grants the right to buy the stock (or asset) at the agreed (set) price within the agreed period. This premium is called the option price (payment, reward). The higher this price, the better it is for the seller (issuer). The lower it is, the better it is for the client. The price that satisfies both parties is called the alternative price, and symbols such as C , "c", C_N , c_N , C_T are used for it. To determine this price, we will examine the profits and costs of both parties.

Let's assume the option contract has been concluded, and the client pays a premium C . In this case, the client's profit at the end of the period will be:

$$f_N(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N) - C,$$

the seller's profit will be:

$$C - f_N(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N),$$

the price of the option being equivalent can be expressed as:

$$f_N(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N) - C = C - f_N(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N)$$

from this, it follows that:

$$C = f_N(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N)$$

here, the values $(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N)$ are assumed to be known in advance. However, if we consider their randomness in practice, the alternative price would be the expected value, which can be written as:

$$C = Ef_N(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N).$$

Thus, from the above considerations, it can be concluded that the types of options can vary based on the expiration date of the option contract, the agreed price, and

the form of the objective function. Below, we present the most commonly encountered and important types of options and their models in option theory and practice.

I. European-style options:

1) European-style standard call option – a purchase option. It is an option contract that grants the right to buy a stock at an agreed price (K) on the agreed expiration date (N). In this case, as emphasized earlier, the payoff function for the buyer of the stock takes the form of $f_N = (S_N - K)^+$. On the other hand, this value represents the amount (size) of the issuer's obligation at the expiration date, $n = N$. When $S_N > K$, the buyer purchases the stock at price K and sells it at price S_N , achieving a payoff of $f_N = (S_N - K)^+$. When $S_N < K$, the buyer does not purchase the stock and only incurs a cost equal to the premium amount (C).

2) The European put option is a type of contract that gives the buyer (holder) the right, but not the obligation, to sell a specific asset (such as a stock) to the issuer at a specified price (K) within a given time frame (N). In this case, the investor (buyer) purchases the stock at the market price (S_N) and then sells it back to the issuer at the predetermined price K , as stipulated by the option. The holder will have a profit if $f_N = (K - S_N)^+$, meaning the option's payoff is the difference between the strike price and the market price if it's positive. The issuer, on the other hand, will bear the liability equal to this value.

3) A call option (also known as a voratnik) contract has the following payoff (the client's profit or the issuer's obligation):

$$f_N = \min\{\max(K_1, S_N), K_2\}, 0 < K_1 < K_2$$

where $0 < K_1 < K_2$ are fixed numbers.

4) The Boston option payoff (the client's profit or the issuer's obligation) is as follows:

$$f_N = \max\{S_N - K_1, 0\} - (K_2 - K_1).$$

The payoff (profit, claim) function in these options depends not only on the final stock price S_N at the last moment and the agreed (strike) price K , but also on all the previous stock prices from S_0 to S_N . In other words, the payoff function is given by:

$$f_N = f_N(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N)$$

This means that the payoff depends on all the past stock prices, making this option a natural generalization of the first and second types (European) options.

5) The European-type look-back call option, i.e., the profit derived from purchasing the stock, depends not only on the stock price at the final moment N but also on the previous stock prices at earlier moments. The payoff (profit, claim, payment) function for this option takes the following form:

$$f_N = (S_N - K_N)^+,$$

$$K_N = \min(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N) = S_N - \min S_n, \quad 0 \leq n \leq N.$$

6) The European-type look-back put option

$$f_N = (K_N - S_N)^+,$$

$$K_N = \max(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N) = \max S_n - S_N, \quad 0 \leq n \leq N.$$

II. Asian-type options.

1). Asian arithmetical call option

$$f_N = (\overline{S}_N - K)^+, \quad \overline{S}_N = \frac{1}{N+1} \sum_{k=0}^N S_k.$$

2) Asian arithmetical put option

$$f_N = (K - \overline{S}_N)^+, \quad \overline{S}_N = \frac{1}{N+1} \sum_{k=0}^N S_k.$$

III. American-type options.

In American option types, the form of the payoff function is slightly different. This is because, in this type, the exercise of the option can be demanded at any time during the contract's term, at an arbitrary moment n , $0 \leq n \leq N$. For example, the option holder may choose to exercise a put option when the stock price falls to its lowest level, or, in the case of a call option, the holder may choose to exercise when the stock price rises to its highest level. Therefore, for this type of option, the payoff (goal, obligation, claim) function is:

$$f_N = f_\tau = \max f_n \quad \text{or} \quad f_N = f_\tau = \min f_n, \quad 0 \leq n \leq N$$

the payoff function is determined in the following form. Here, f_n is defined similarly to the European-type options for both call and put options. f_τ represents the moment of exercise τ ($0 \leq \tau \leq N$), also known as the stopping time or the moment when the

obligation is exercised. This is a random variable because it depends on the random quantities $(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N)$.

**FOR A EUROPEAN-TYPE OPTION, IN THE DISCRETE SETTING,
EVALUATING THE KEY INDICATORS OF A COMPLETE MARKET.**

Let's assume that in a complete market (B, S) , the investor's initial capital is $X_0 = x$, with a self-financing portfolio (strategy) $\pi = (\beta, \nu)$, and the payoff obligation with the objective function f_N is such that almost everywhere $X_N^\pi = f_N$. In this case, we know that the corresponding arbitrage-free price for this payoff obligation is $x = C_N = C(f_N)$. Below, we will calculate the initial capital $x = C_N = C(f_N)$ for the payoff obligation f_N in such a (B, S) market, and construct the strategy $\pi = (\beta, \nu)$ that satisfies this task, using an example of a European-type option.

Theorem: In a complete market (B, S) , there exists a self-financing perfect strategy $\pi = (\beta, \nu)$ corresponding to the payoff obligation f_N .

1) Formula for calculating the arbitrage-free price:

$$C_N = C(f_N) = B_0 E \left(\frac{f_N}{B_N} \right) = (1 + r)^{-N} E f_N .$$

2) Formula for calculating the investor's capital corresponding to the hedging strategy π at the k -th moment of the time interval.

$$X_k^\pi = B_k E \left(\frac{f_N}{B_N} \middle| \mathfrak{F}_k \right), k = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1.$$

3) The stock position ν_k at the k -th moment for the perfect strategy π is determined by the following equation:

$$\Delta \frac{X_k}{B_k} = \nu_k * \Delta \frac{S_k}{B_k}, k = 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

4) The size of the bank deposits (bonds) β_k at the k -th moment for the perfect strategy π is calculated using the following formulas:

$$\beta_k = \frac{X_k^\pi - \nu_k * S_k}{B_k}, k = 1, 2, \dots, N .$$

or

$$\beta_k = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=0}^k \nu_i * \Delta \left(\frac{S_i}{B_i} \right), k = 1, 2, \dots, N .$$

CONCLUSION

The problem of financial resource shortfall or increasing capital can be solved not only through credit, borrowing, or lending, but also by issuing, selling, or purchasing securities. Securities refer to legal documents that confirm the ownership share of a person in the property and income derived from the property of an enterprise or organization (regardless of the form of ownership). These documents also provide the possibility of transferring the rights derived from them to other parties. Securities can exist in the form of certificates, documents, or entries in accounts, and may be used in settlements or as collateral for loans. The issuance of securities is called an emission, and those who issue them are called issuers. Issuers can include joint-stock companies, banks, governments, investment companies or funds, local authorities, and other legal entities. Legal entities and individuals who purchase securities with their own funds to earn a return are called investors. Individuals are referred to as individual investors, while financial institutions, pension funds, investment companies, funds, banks, and insurance companies are referred to as institutional investors. The issue of determining the alternative prices of options is of great importance, as it helps prevent the emergence of arbitrage situations. Traditional methods applied to other financial instruments do not allow for the accurate determination of option value, since the risk indicator changes in accordance with the fluctuations in the value of the underlying assets and their duration.

The self-financing initial capital $X_0 = x$ will be the option price. This price is the contract condition and is calculated as the alternative price derived from the payment obligation f_N , which will be equal to the amount of

$$X_0 = x = C_N = (1 + r)^{-N} E f_N$$

Thus, in these cases, the investor forms their portfolio $\pi_k = (\beta_k, \nu_k)$ where β_k and ν_k for $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$ are determined through the above formulas. It is clear from these stages how the strategy can be constructed. Now, the results obtained above should be applied to the explicit form of the obligation function f_N that is, to derive the results related to the pricing of European-style options and the formation of the investor's portfolio.

In conclusion, the best methods for calculating option price valuation are the binomial and Black-Scholes model approaches, through which we can assess the value of an option.

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